

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Sowing cover crops is economically justified, even for complex mixtures, given their benefits for soil quality and biodiversity and their low impact on gross margins

Do species diverse cover crop mixtures enhance soil biodiversity and main crop yield/quality in organic agriculture? That was the central question in a trial at Inagro in Belgium. Additionally, was tested whether (1) diverser mixtures combine more soil benefiting functions, like N-fixation; (2) including leguminous species in the mix, delivered additional N to the main crops. Following mixtures were sown in summer/autumn before subsequent spring/summer crops: broccoli (2021), red beet ('22) and potato ('23):

- Phacelia + black oat (BAU);
- Phacelia + Egyptian Clover (Mix1);
- 5 species mix (Phacelia, black oat, Egyptian clover, vetch and fodder radish) (Mix2);
- 12 species mix (Mix2 + forage radish, pea, lupin, serradella, niger, alsike clover, flax) (Mix 3).

The 5-species mix (Mix2) appeared to be the best agricultural practice, showing these benefits:

- High and stable aboveground cover crop biomass production;
- Increased nitrogen availability to subsequent crops, thus improving soil fertility;
- Improved biodiversity, particularly for genes related to denitrification and cycling of excess nitrate;
- Increased potato marketable yield;
- Maintenance of economic profitability: Mix2 is most expensive (price/kg and applied dose), resulting in higher total direct costs. However, the impact of these additional costs on the variation in gross margin over treatments and crop cycles is relatively small, as yield and sales revenues have a larger impact.

Overall, the use of complex cover crop mixtures increased costs, and differed in price, but the impact on revenues and gross margins is small. Consequently, sowing cover crops is economically justified, especially for the 5-species mix.

1. Revenue, direct cost and gross margin (euro/ha) per growth season / crop and the totals over the three year rotation

KEYWORDS

Organic agriculture, cover crops, species, mixtures

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